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An Economic Strategic Framework to Guide the Local Government Executives

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ABSTRACT:

This paper presents an economic strategic frame that provides the local government executive heads of Quezon City a roadmap on how to achieve sustainable development for enhanced quality of life among their populace. In so doing, it recognizes the pivotal role of Local Government Units (LGUs) in governance and development while addressing the unique challenges and opportunities confronting Quezon City, a major center of business and commerce in the country. One cannot deny dynamism in the economy and competitiveness of Quezon City, but at the same time, it is swamped with huge challenges to achieve sustainability under a changed climate. This shall then direct efforts toward promoting carbon-neutral and climate-resilient growth, healthy and green urban spaces, and attaining social equity through the Enhanced Local Climate Change Action Plan 2012-2050. The strategic framework is underpinned by four major objectives: economic diversification, sustainable development, infrastructure development, and social inclusion. Economic diversification, by which these sectors are encouraged, includes technology, health, education, tourism, and the creative industry, among others, so that it can help reduce the dependency of a single industry.

Sustainable development is also where one puts into actions that will make everything work in ensuring long-term ecological balance and implementation of climate change mitigation. Infrastructure development involves the growth and renewal of transport and communication systems, social inclusion means that the city must grow and that all inhabitants are beneficiaries of the city's increase. Major programs under this action plan are the Green Public Procurement Program towards a Circular Economy and Sustainable Consumption and the GrowQC program on Food Security, which promotes urban agriculture. The major thrust of the city is investment to make the cities livable through public transportation, upgrading of infrastructure, and implementing smart technology in cities. Financially, there was a good performance for Quezon City. Local Revenues for domestically sourced products have always increased, and regular income per annum has always recorded an incline. Economic development is nowadays planned, and the city is one of the excellent illustrations of sustainable urban development. Always ranked as the Most Competitive City in the Philippines.

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It also provides a full SWOT analysis showing the strengths related to data-driven decisions and stakeholder integration, and identifies weaknesses in resource needs and resistance to change. A set of practical guidelines in the document will be provided to LGU executives for the tailoring of local economic development plans and attraction of investments and for them to undertake appropriate training programs in support of strategic initiatives. The strategic economic framework should, therefore, be able to empower Quezon City to face up to challenges of development by harnessing any available opportunities for growth and embracing forward-looking practices that promote not only economic resilience but also improvement in general well-being.

Keywords: *Economic Strategic Framework, Financial Performance, Local Government Executive, Local Government Units, Strategic Planning*

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